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3RD SCIENCE FAIR DECOLAR AND NAIPCE SCIENCE CLUB: RESEARCH DEVELOPMENT IN SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Research in schools is essential for developing curiosity in students, and the science fair can help in the training process of young researchers, so that the students involved can develop all stages of the scientific method. In this sense, the NAIPCE extension actions center in partnership with the Decolar Science Club has helped in the development of the science fair in the municipality of Nova Mutum-MT. In 2023, the third edition was held, with the presentation of 44 works developed by students from the municipality, in addition to the participation of more than a thousand students in the workshops and visits to the works. The workshops were taught by Unemat academics, sharing the students' knowledge with the community. Therefore, research in schools is essential for developing curiosity, carried out through the search for answers to the small problems they develop.